

STUDY INITIATION PACKAGE

Deliverable D2.12

Study initiation package

HIGH HORIZONS – D2.12

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Author(s)	Varvara A. Mouchtouri, Michalis Koureas, Maria Kyritsi, Fani Kalala, Mattheos Speletas, Christos Hadjichristodoulou
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1 Description of the clinical study

1.1 Title, acronym, unique identifier of the clinical study

The title of the clinical study: Prospective mother-child birth cohort study of the effect of heat exposure on health.

The acronym of the clinical study is: HH BirthCo.

The unique identifier is not applicable.

1.2 Study rationale

The present study will be conducted under the HIGH Horizons project which aims at producing evidence-informed quantifiable indicators for monitoring the health impact of extreme heat among pregnant and postpartum women, newborns and infants, as well as defining cut-off thresholds for an Early Warning System for certain risk groups. HIGH Horizons in its current work plan will produce evidence through analysis of environmental and health outcomes data in Europe and sub-Saharan Africa, as well as through systematic literature reviews and does not include methods for investigating the mechanisms that heat affects health of the project study population. The proposed study will help to understand the biological and thermal physiological pathways from heat effects on adverse health outcomes to pregnant women and children up to one year of age. Results are expected to help to identify individual risk factors and inform prevention strategies. Exposure to elevated temperature has been identified as risk factor for adverse maternal, fetal, and infant health outcomes in numerous studies. The most frequently assessed outcomes include preterm birth, birth weight and stillbirth. Previous research indicate that heat exposure can initiate various processes potentially harmful to the mother or fetus including decrease in placental blood flow, dehydration, and inflammatory responses. More evidence is needed to elucidate the mechanisms by which heat exposure can cause adverse outcomes. There is a vital need for research to determine the causes of adverse pregnancy outcomes associated with heat exposure, in order to manage the effects of climate change in pregnant women and fetuses. Thus, the pathophysiological mechanisms to unravel the investigated exposure effect relationship merit further investigation.

Moreover, evidence is accumulating which suggests that maternal exposures and life-style patterns can have an impact on an offspring's health, affecting endocrine status and neurodevelopment, and increasing the risk for developing chronic diseases including obesity, asthma/allergies, metabolic syndromes and autism spectrum disorders. These aspects are studied by implementing large prospective cohort studies, recruiting mother-child pairs and continuously monitoring exposures (from conception and onwards) and outcomes over a long time period which could even reach the person's adulthood. These studies provide the scientific community with valuable information to address the complexity of emerging environmental health issues. Apart from heat, exposures can include toxicants in the general environment and in workplaces, diet, lifestyle choices and even socioeconomic status. Capturing a person's exposure to a wide variety of factors requires diverse approaches for recording and evaluating internal and external exposures, characteristics, lifestyle, physiology and genetic factors. These approaches consist of a combination of self-reported tools (questionnaires/indexes), environmental or personalized monitoring, sensor technologies, exposure models and most importantly, the detection and quantification of biological markers of exposure, effect and susceptibility. "Omic" technologies (transcriptomics, genomics/epigenomics, proteomics and metabolomics) are invaluable for documenting and understanding the potential causal associations between in utero exposures and adverse effects.

1.2.1 Extent and evaluation of current knowledge directly linked to the scientific question(s) to be answered by the clinical study

HIGH Horizons project partners in their previous studies have demonstrated exposure to elevated temperature as risk factor for adverse maternal, fetal, and infant health outcomes (Chersich et al., 2020). The HIGH Horizons team's systematic reviews identified 200+ studies revealing heat's detrimental impacts on maternal and newborn health, including preterm birth, stillbirth, congenital anomalies, pre-eclampsia, and more. Most studies were in high-income countries, but concerns extend beyond. Another review (unpublished) located 120 studies on extreme heat's negative effects on children under two. Limited interventions exist, and indirect impacts on pregnant women and infants also require further investigation.

Moreover, measurement of specific biomarkers during pregnancy and in infants can further elucidate the role of heat exposure to adverse health effects. Pregnant women are particularly vulnerable to heat stress, due to a variety of factors including increased body weight, decreased surface area to body mass, which increased fetal metabolic rate (Dalugoda et al., 2022). The adverse impact on pregnancy is explained through mechanisms involving reduction in placental blood flow, dehydration, and inflammatory responses. While it is clear that pregnant and postpartum women, and infants are heavily affected by climate change, these populations have received little attention to date in climate change policies. Furthermore, there is substantial lack of concise evidence regarding the causes behind the effect of high ambient temperatures on pregnancy and no biomarker has been identified to be the most useful in predicting the adverse outcomes on pregnant women and fetuses considering that from the biomarkers that are mentioned in the literature some have not been studied in humans, e.g. the levels of oxytocin and prostaglandins in pregnant women upon heat stress.

1.2.2 Outcomes (efficacy, safety) of completed and number of ongoing clinical studies utilising the same intervention in the same indication (including review of public registers)

This study is an observational cohort without interventions.

1.2.3 Level of evidence related to the mechanism of action of the intervention in the planned clinical study population

This study is an observational cohort without interventions.

Heat stress may cause alterations of intracellular and extracellular heat shock proteins (HSP), which may have an impact on placental function (Bonell et al., 2020; Jee et al., 2021; Ziegert et al., 1999). Accumulating evidence suggests that endometrial and uterine cells have an abundance of HSPs, implying their possible involvement during the pregnancy process (Jee et al., 2021). HSPs have been found to be associated with decidualization, implantation and placentation, with their dysregulation associated with implantation failure, pregnancy loss and other feto-maternal complications (Jee et al., 2021). Furthermore, HSP is also associated with stress response, specifically in modulating the ER stress, a critical determinant for reproductive success (Jee et al., 2021). HSP70 levels have been associated with preeclampsia (Saghafi et al., 2018).

Cortisol, adrenaline, cytokines, and other inflammatory markers can be released as a result of oxidative stress caused by heat stress (Dreiling et al., 1991; McMorris et al., 2006; Samuels et al., 2022; Selkirk et al., 2008; Wang et al., 2015). Although this has not yet been confirmed in heat-stressed pregnant women, it has been hypothesized that this inflammatory cascade may cause premature labour as a result of inflammation at the maternal foetal interface or an increase in foetal and placental prostaglandin release (Gronlund et al., 2020; Peltier, 2003; Samuels et al., 2022; Schifano et al., 2013). Preeclampsia, premature birth, recurrent miscarriage, and infertility are associated with altered cytokine profiles, which are frequently accompanied by elevated IL6 levels (Prins et al., 2012).

Dehydration as a consequence of heat exposure has also been suggested as another cause of preterm birth (Gronlund et al., 2020; Lajinian et al., 2011; Samuels et al., 2022; Schifano et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2020). The potential mechanism includes i) reduction in uterine blood flow that can trigger prostaglandin release, and ii) the release of antidiuretic hormone (ADH, a hormone engaged in water retention to stave against dehydration), as oxytocin is released simultaneously, it has been hypothesised that this could trigger preterm labour, iii) excessive sweating and insufficient hydration in hot and humid environments or intensive physical work (Guinn et al., 1997; Theobald, 1959; Vähä-Eskeli et al., 1991).

1.3 Objective(s) of the clinical study

The overall aim of the study is to investigate the effects of heat exposure on pregnant women, fetuses, and newborns and to provide insights into the potential mechanisms governing the impacts of heat related exposures on maternal and child health.

Specific objectives

The specific objectives of the study include the following:

- to monitor maternal heat exposure during different stages of pregnancy and early childhood (up to 1 year) in the outdoor and indoor environment including occupational heat exposure,
- to examine the relationship between heat exposure and health outcomes for the mother and the child

- to identify confounding variables for the relationship of heat exposure with maternal-fetal-child health outcomes.
- to examine the effect of heat exposure in the level of specific biomarkers.
- to identify individual risk factors and inform prevention strategies
- to provide evidence-based recommendations and insights to inform public health policies, guidelines, and interventions aimed at minimizing the adverse effects of heat exposure on pregnant women, fetuses, and newborns.

1.4 Characteristics of the study population

The initial enrolment will include 500 pregnant women recruited at regular outpatient clinics located at three sites at the first appointment (1st trimester of pregnancy). The sites include University General Hospital ATTIKON (Chaidari, Greece), Alexandra Maternity Hospital (Athens, Greece) and the General Hospital of Larissa (Larissa, Greece). The number of participants was selected to be sufficient to identify differences in biomarkers between exposed and unexposed individuals accounting for drop-out. Exclusion criteria will include any condition or disease that, according to the researcher's judgement, could make the inclusion unsafe or unfeasible (e.g. serious medical or mental conditions/diseases).

Details on sample size and power calculation

Power analysis was conducted by using the G*Power (version 3.1.9.7) software. For the purposes of the analysis, the 75th percentile of ambient temperature data was selected as a cut-off value. The outcome is defined as levels of specific biomarkers related to heat stress (cortisol, adrenaline, heat shock proteins, CRP, dehydration markers). As the sample size is also limited by other parameters (mainly the cost of laboratory analysis) and since multiple outcomes will be assessed, we performed a sensitivity analysis to determine the minimum effect size that can be identified with a sample size that can be supported by the available resources and capacity, in order to assess the feasibility of the investigations. By selecting a sample size of 400 pregnant women, a confidence level 95% and a study power of 80% an effect size of $d = 0.324$ can be identified, with assays of the t-test family. This lies between small and medium effect size according to Cohen criteria, practically indicating that the sample is sufficient to identify a minimum difference of

about a third of a standard deviation. Since the initial enrolment will be 500 persons, the sample is sufficient even if a proportion drops out.

1.5 Design of the clinical study

The study is based on a prospective cohort design and specifically a mother-child birth cohort design. The longitudinal birth cohort study design follows a group of participants from early pregnancy through delivery, collecting data during several follow ups. It allows for the assessment of maternal exposures, maternal-fetal health outcomes, and neonatal outcomes over time, providing data to better understand the chronological aspect of the exposure-effect relationships. The study is observational and does not include any interventions. This design has numerous advantages compared to other types of observational epidemiological studies (such as case control, cross sectional, retrospective cohort) as the exposure-effect continuum can be captured and identified more accurately, and it is less prone to biases. Moreover, a birth-cohort design allows the investigation of the relationship between pre-natal exposure and effect in the offspring.

1.6 Type of intervention

This study is an observational cohort without interventions.

1.7 Description and timing of study procedures

Pregnant women will be recruited at the participating clinics during the 1st trimester of pregnancy. Women will be followed until delivery, and 2 additional appointments will take place at the 2nd and 3rd trimester of pregnancy. After delivery, newborns will be followed until 12 months of age. The following data will be obtained:

- 1) Basic Personal Data, (name, surname, ID number, internal study code, etc.)
- 2) Contact Data (phone number, email, home address)
- 3) Questionnaire data (responses to questionnaires, information about lifestyle, occupation, anthropometric data, data on your exposure to high temperatures, etc.)
- 4) Demographic Data (Racial data, socioeconomic status data, age, weight, height, etc.)
- 5) Health data (state of health, medical history)
- 6) Genetic Data-Sample Data (samples, biomarkers, etc.)

Moreover, a critical aspect of the participation concerns the provision of biological samples during pregnancy and at delivery. Furthermore, participants will be asked to approve and facilitate the conduction of environmental measurements at the residence.

A detailed description of Recruitment & follow ups, Questionnaire data, Clinical examination data, Outcome measurements, Environmental/ climate data & Heat exposure assessment, Sample collection & management, Laboratory analyses and Statistical analysis is provided in **annex 1**.

2 Preparedness status

2.1 Development of the clinical study protocol

2.1.1 Scientific advice from regulatory and health technology assessment bodies

Not applicable. Advice will be asked from the UTH ethics committee about ethics in research and there is no need to ask scientific advice about a regulatory and health technology assessment bodies.

2.1.2 Clinical efficacy, safety, and methodological guidelines (including guidelines on statistics)

The laboratory analyses will be conducted at the Laboratory of Hygiene and Epidemiology of the University of Thessaly a Biosafety Hazard 2 Laboratory. Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assays (ELISA) will be used to measure HSP levels, hormones, cytokines, Interleukines and CRP. For gene expression, whole blood samples will be analysed using targeted analysis of known RNAs and heat shock protein gene expression panels (GEPs). Furthermore, transcriptome analysis will be paired with proteomic analysis in high-throughput instruments such as MALDI-TOF MS. For the immunological, molecular and proteomic tests mentioned above, CE IVD kits will be used strictly under the manufacturer's instructions. Moreover, all laboratory analyses will be performed on validated equipment.

Statistical analysis will involve various methods to investigate the relationship between heat exposure, biomarker levels, birth outcomes and outcomes on the children. Also, confounding and synergistic effects of covariables will be assessed. At minimum, conventional statistical tests and methods (e.g. student's t-test, Pearson chi-square,

Mann-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis tests, Spearman and Pearson correlation coefficients) will be applied. Risk estimates for categorical independent variables will be determined by calculating relative risks or odds ratios for logistic regression analyses. Principal component analysis will be used for dimension reduction. Study findings will be critically interpreted under the current knowledge on possible underlying mechanisms explaining the identified associations]

2.1.3 Involvement of citizens / patients, carers in drawing up the clinical study protocol

Feasibility assessment will be conducted during the pilot testing of questionnaire. During the pilot phase pregnant women and their husbands will be invited to participate and provide feedback.

2.2 Regulatory intelligence to ensure timely regulatory approval and ethics clearance of the clinical study in all jurisdictions where its implementation is planned

2.2.1 How the consortium will ensure access to regulatory expertise necessary to get advice on, and management of, regulatory affairs activities in all concerned jurisdictions?

UTH researchers have access to the experts of UTH about ethics and legal aspects and data protection. For any question from the ethics committee to the UTH team that cannot be answered by the UTH team, team members will ask advice from the UTH experts on ethics and legal aspects. When needed the team can seek advice from the external and/or two internal ethics advisors of the HIGH Horizons project.

2.2.2 How the consortium will ensure access to ethics expertise necessary to get advice on current proceedings and documentation requirements of all concerned ethics committees?

UTH researchers have access to the experts of UTH about ethics and legal aspects and data protection. For any question from the ethics committee to the UTH team that cannot be answered by the UTH team, team members will ask advice from the UTH experts on ethics and legal aspects. When needed the team can seek advice from the external legal advisor-contractor and/or two internal ethics advisors of the HIGH Horizons project. Moreover, the protocol will be submitted for approval from the scientific committees of all the participating sites.

2.3 How the scientific and operational governance of the clinical study will be ensured?

2.3.1 Please give details about the sponsor(s) (name, type of entity, seat or country of residence).

Not applicable

2.3.2 Please describe the composition, the role and the functioning of the planned board(s), governing bodies.

There will be no boards or governing bodies specifically established for the current study. The study will follow the rules of the governing bodies of HIGH Horizons (e.g. Steering Committee, Scientific Advisory Board). As far as the birth cohort scientific working group is concerned its composition includes expert gynaecologists, paediatricians, nutritionists, epidemiologists and is as follows :

- group leader Prof. C. Hadjichristodoulou
- Members : Prof. M. Speletas, Assoc. Prof. B. Mouchtouri, Assist. Prof. F. Kalala, Prof. V. Papaevangelou, Prof. I. Grivea, Prof. P. Drakakis, Prof. G. Daskalakis, Dr H. Skentou, Prof. A. Naska, Prof. V. Mpenetou, Lecturer Dr M. Grammatikopoulou

3 Operational feasibility

3.1 Please describe how the availability of the intervention(s) (including comparators) is secured throughout the entire implementation phase (give details on manufacturing, packaging / labelling operations, storage, logistical, import/export issues, etc.)

Not applicable. The study does not involve intervention.

3.2 Please describe how the study population will be recruited

3.2.1 Please give details on the recruitment strategy, monitoring of progress and potential mitigation measures

Pregnant women who have planned an ultrasound scan at 12 weeks of gestation will be informed about the study and their potential involvement by their doctor. Women will be given as much time as they need to study the information letter and if needed they will be given online counselling meeting to clarify the study aims and procedures. For women who agree to participate study's staff will be present at the first ultrasound appointment and provide study material, information sheets and obtain a consent form. Midwives and obstetricians will have an active role in encouraging participation. After signing the

consent form, the processes of data collection and biospecimen collection will be initiated. The above processes will be computerized. Follow up appointments will be arranged in collaboration with the participant and the participating clinic. All involved staff, including researchers, nurses, or other personnel, will be trained on the study procedures, ethical considerations, and effective communication strategies. Regular communication will be encouraged to ensure regular and reliable follow ups.

3.2.2 How many clinical sites will contribute to the recruitment of the study population in which countries? Are these clinical sites part of an established clinical trial network? Please also describe the selection criteria of the clinical sites.

The sites include University General Hospital ATTIKON (Chaidari, Greece), Alexandra Maternity Hospital (Athens, Greece) and the General Hospital of Larissa (Larissa, Greece). Additionally, Iaso Maternity Clinic (Maroussi, Greece) and Nicosia Maternity Clinic (Nicosia, Cyprus) will be included as well. The above sites are not an established clinical trial network. They were selected primarily because of the wide variety of experts they comprise of and the clinical experience they have on pregnancies and the number of pregnant women they follow.

3.2.3 Will recruitment of the study population be of competitive nature between the clinical sites? (Please describe how underperformance of individual clinical sites in recruitment will be managed.)

The recruitment of the study population will not be of competitive nature since the clinical sites will be a part of an established network and will work in a complementary manner with good cooperation covering a wide range of pregnancies from different socioeconomic backgrounds. For example, the General Hospital of Larissa will provide data from women with low income whilst the private clinics from women with high income.

3.2.4 What evidence supports the ability of the individual clinical sites to recruit the required number of study participants within the planned timeline (e.g. documented performance in previous clinical studies of similar complexity targeting very similar study population)?

The clinical sites were chosen amongst others because they are characterised by a substantial number of births (for example, the General Hospital of Larisa alone has ~150

births/year, the Alexandra Maternity Hospital has ~1500 births/year). This fact renders the required number of study participants feasible within the planned timeline.

3.3 Please describe what additional supply (e.g. an electronic device for remote data capture, a specific instrument for administering the investigational product, etc.) is necessary to carry out the required study procedures and how this supply will be made available to the clinical sites

Indoor temperature and humidity measurements will be conducted to assess heat exposure of the participants. For this purpose, data will be collected using HOBO UX100-0031 temperature and humidity loggers or other equivalent equipment. A proportion of participants will be equipped with small mobile sensors that measure and record air temperature at 5-minute intervals

3.4 Please provide plans on data management aspects (data standards, type of data capture, verification of data, central data collection, cleaning, analysis, reporting, security)

Personal data will be processed anonymously and in an aggregated way (personal data collected from HIGH Horizons will be treated as highly confidential, respecting privacy) with GDPR-compliance in mind. Participants in projects activities will be given clear information about how their data will be collected and protected during the project and either destroyed or reused at the end of the research. The project coordinator will provide and/or confirm with all partners with detailed procedures for recruitment of participants and data collection. Data storage (paper & digital: quantitative databases, qualitative audiotapes and transcriptions) will be secured and access by unwanted third parties will be prevented. Data storage will be protected against disaster and risk in compliance with the ISO/IEC 27001:2005 standards.

GDPR-compliant procedures for data collection, storage, protection, retention, destruction, or re-use as well as data safety procedures will be developed in the Data Management Plan. The DMP will outline the types of data collected and/or produced during the project, the procedures to elaborate and share them among partners and toward external stakeholders, including the public. The document will be prepared according to the Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon2020 addressing specifically

¹ <https://www.onsetcomp.com/products/data-loggers/ux100-003>

the Data set, Data description, standards and meta-data, Data sharing policies, archiving and presentations. Data sharing policies will define which data will be accessible and visible by whom.

3.5 Please give details on how reporting obligations (regarding study initiation, safety of study participants, ethical concerns, quality issues, integrity of data, study results) to regulatory bodies and ethics committees will be met.

UTH researchers' team will be responsible to report to the ethics committee any change in the study protocol that might take place after getting the ethics approval. Any other obligation for reporting to the ethics committee will be completed by the UTH researchers' team. The study does not involve a regulatory body.

3.6 Please list all items of the sponsor's responsibilities (e.g. monitoring clinical sites, meeting regulatory obligations, data management, etc.) that will be supported by entities that are not part of the sponsor's organisation. Please describe how the sponsor will ensure oversight of these activities.

Not applicable, there are no sponsors.

3.7 What are the plans for major study milestones and what evidence supports its feasibility?

Study has been approved by the 81 / 31 - 07 – 2023 decision of the UTH Ethics committee (Annex 2).

Milestones

- (i) completion of recruitment of the study population: between month 6 and month 30 of the project duration
- (ii) final assessment of all study participants: between month 6 and month 42 of the project timeline.
- (iii) analysis and reporting of the study results: between month 42 and month 46 of the project timeline.

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5 Annexes

5.1 Annex 1: Research study protocol

To access ANNEX 1, please click on the link below and use the following credentials:

https://uthnoc-my.sharepoint.com/:b:/g/personal/high-horizons-rep_o365_uth_gr/ESmyTQZm9ENGn2LXQFF_SBABzMXaGAUqKKT3ZVRZg-U_rA?e=PIF7DY

Passcode: **2121**

5.2 Annex 2: Decision of the Ethics Committee of the University of Thessaly

To access ANNEX 2, please click on the link below and use the following credentials:

https://uthnoc-my.sharepoint.com/:b:/g/personal/high-horizons-rep_o365_uth_gr/EYLexSfM9pdFkGbnRt_smPkBPM9UuE6ehupJDpkgZ-M7iA?e=q5JJYW

Passcode: **2121**